

Additional file 8. Proportion of expressed and differentially expressed genes for each soil microorganism.

Microbial strain	Genes^a	Expressed genes (%)^b		Differentially expressed genes (%)^c	
<i>Azorhizobium caulinodans</i> ORS 571	4,781	4,166	(87)	993	(24)
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> subsp. <i>subtilis</i> 168	4,371	1,406	(32)	175	(12)
<i>Cupriavidus metallidurans</i> CH34	6,829	6,187	(91)	2,333	(38)
<i>Pseudomonas protegens</i> Pf-5	6,212	6,177	(99)	5,093	(82)
<i>Debaryomyces hansenii</i> CBS767	6,272	5,830	(93)	2,776	(48)
<i>Pichia stipitis</i> CBS 6054	5,807	5,674	(98)	3,645	(64)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> S288c	7,126	6,145	(86)	2,640	(43)
<i>Schizosaccharomyces pombe</i> 972h	7,018	5,171	(74)	1,238	(24)
<i>Aspergillus niger</i> CBS 513.88	14,445	10,087	(70)	3,217	(32)
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f. sp. <i>lycopersici</i> 4287	18,066	10,085	(56)	4,043	(40)
<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i> Wisconsin54-1255	13,671	9,088	(66)	2,156	(24)
<i>Trichoderma atroviride</i> IMI 206040 ^d	11,863	7,398	(62)	88	(1)
<i>Armillaria mellea</i> DSM 3731 ^e	14,473	3,926	(27)	8	(0)

^a Number of genes of the reference genome (genome databases are reported in Table 1).

^b Mean number of expressed genes in at least one condition and the corresponding percentage (%) of total genes in the reference genome.

^c Number of differentially expressed genes and the corresponding percentage (%) of expressed genes. The Pearson's correlation coefficient between numbers of expressed and differentially expressed genes was 0.53 ($P = 0.06$).

^d The reference genome of *Trichoderma atroviride* IMI 206040 was used to align read pairs derived from *Trichoderma atroviride* SC1.

^e The reference genome of *Armillaria mellea* DSM 3731 was used to align read pairs derived from *Armillaria mellea* M6132.